

Description of a new species of *Aporrhais* (Gastropoda, Stromboidea) from the Upper Eocene of Western Siberia

Ulrich Wieneke¹, Pavel V. Smirnov², Anton Maslennikov³, Yaroslav S. Trubin^{4,5}

¹ Hagener Str. 18a, 82418 Murnau, Germany

² Kazan Federal University, Kremlyovskaya 18, 420111 Kazan, Russia

³ Parohodskaya Str. 4, apart.70, 625002, Tyumen, Russia

⁴ University of Bonn, Nussallee 8, 53115 Bonn, Germany

⁵ Tomsk State University, Lenin Avenue 36, 634050 Tomsk, Russia

<https://zoobank.org/2206DE74-F92F-411F-A5FE-9AE915C19E75>

Corresponding author: Ulrich Wieneke (stromboidea@gmail.com)

Academic editor: Alexander Nützel ♦ Received 5 June 2024 ♦ Accepted 26 November 2024 ♦ Published 11 December 2024

Abstract

Material from the Upper Eocene Tavda Formation of Western Siberia contains a new species, *Aporrhais siberica* sp. nov. It has been misidentified as *A. cornuta* Korobkov, 1949, an aporrhaid originally described from the Upper Eocene / Lower Oligocene of the Turan Sea. The main difference between *A. siberica* and *A. cornuta* is the missing spire-adnate digitation of *A. siberica*. Publications referencing both morphologies are analyzed, and revised synonymies are presented.

Keywords

Aporrhaidae, Paleogene, Siberia, Tavda Formation, Taxonomy

Introduction

The Eocene and Oligocene marine fauna of the East Peri-Tethys and adjacent regions contains several gastropod morphs of the family Aporrhaidae (Ryabinin and Korobkov 1949; Il'ina 1953; Alekseev 1963; Amitrov 2005), which are usually lumped under the name *Aporrhais cornuta* Korobkov, 1949 that was originally described from the Oligocene of the North Aral region. New fossil aporrhaid material from the Trans-Ural region of Western Siberia, collected in recent years (Popov et al. 2019), is examined in this publication, and a new species from that region is described, replacing Turbina's (1959, 1962) attribution to "*Aporrhais cornutus* Alexeiev". The similar *A. cornuta* from the Paleogene of North Aral is re-evaluated herein and compared to the new species.

Material and methods

The research material encompasses six lots and was collected in the Kyshtyrla quarry (55°55'15"N, 65°49'26"E), situated on the south-western periphery of Western Siberia, which is recognized as the Trans-Ural region (Fig. 1). The material is stored in the Museum of the Tyumen Industrial University (MTIU) and the Slovtsov Museum Complex of Tyumen (SMCT) (Tyumen, Russia).

Based on detailed studies of pollen, dinoflagellate cysts, and magnetostratigraphy, the Tavda Formation is considered as Middle and Upper Eocene in age (Akhmet'ev et al. 2004, 2010, 2012; Iakovleva 2000, 2011; Iakovleva and Heilmann-Clausen 2010; Gnibidenko et al. 2020; Kuzmina et al. 2021). Further stratigraphic and paleoenvironmental information on the formation has been provided by

Figure 1. Location of the Kyshtyrla quarry and stratigraphic subdivision of the Tavda Formation after Gribidenko et al. (2020) and Kuzmina et al. (2021).

foraminiferal assemblages (Subbotina et al. 1964; Podobina 1975, 1998, 2020). In this context, we note that the Kyshtyrla Quarry is a unique site where nearly all recent important palaeogeographical insights about the Eocene of the West Siberian Sea were made, including findings of shark teeth (Malyskina 2006, 2012, 2021), Teleostei bone remains (Marrama et al. 2019), otoliths (Schwarzshans et al. 2021), mollusks (Trubin 2018; Popov et al. 2019), and trace fossils (Nesterov et al. 2018). Recent foraminiferal studies, accompanied by geochemical data, indicate that the quarry deposits belong to the Tavda Formation, recognized as Upper Eocene (Trubin et al. 2024) and associated with a shallow subtidal environment at the stage of increasing isolation of the West Siberian Basin from the world ocean.

The quarry is approximately 15 m deep. The deposits are polymineralic illite-smectite and montmorillonite blue-green clays with admixtures of pyrite, marcasite, siderite, quartz, and gypsum (Smirnov et al. 2019).

Sedimentary processes reflect the dynamics of a semi-isolated epicontinental sea in shallow-water environments during the Late Eocene. (Akhmet'ev et al. 2010). From the palaeogeographic point of view, the West Siberian Sea was isolated from the Arctic Ocean and connected to the Peri-Tethyan Sea via the Tyrgay Strait (Palcu and Krijgsman 2022); see Fig. 2.

To account for the numerous taxonomic and nomenclature changes a species might have undergone, we utilize chresonymies. This practice provides a comprehensive record of a species's historical names. To be exact, we use the original spelling, although this may lead to different spellings, e. g., for the author's name. While aiming to include all published occurrences, achieving complete coverage can be challenging. Despite our efforts, some entries might be missing. The names in the chresonymy are sorted into two sections. The top ones contain those that belong to the species, and the ones that bear in the reference the according name of the discussed species but do not belong to it begin with "non".

Criteria for classifying the references:

- Primary source evidence: Direct examination of the original material, high-quality figures, or detailed descriptions are prioritized for classification.
- Stratigraphy and geography: When primary source evidence is unavailable, the fossil record's stratigraphy and geographic origin are considered.
- If insufficient information exists for clear categorization, a question mark ("?") precedes the chresonymy entry.

Figure 2. Paleogeography of the Peri-Tethys and subjected basins during the Late Eocene (modified after Akhmet'ev et al. 2012 and Palcu and Krijgsman 2022) and distribution of sites with *Aporrhais siberica* sp. nov.: (1) The Trans-Ural region of Western Siberia (Turbina 1959; Popov et al. 2019; this paper); (2) The central part of the Western Siberia (Turbina 1962); and *Aporrhais cornuta* Korobkov, 1949; (3) Ustyurt (Il'ina 1953, 1955, 1960; Alekseev 1963); (4) Northern Aral Sea region (Korobkov 1949; Ovechkin 1954).

The gastropod terminology is adapted from Manganelli et al. (2008).

Systematic Paleontology

Family Aporrhaidae Gray, 1850

Genus *Aporrhais* Mendes da Costa, 1778

Aporrhais siberica Wieneke & Trubin, sp. nov.

<https://zoobank.org/22207F3B-5AF7-47EB-9409-A1529B948C8D>

Plate 1: figs 1–12

Synonymy.

1959. *Aporrhais cornutus* Alexeiev – Turbina, pp. 30–31, pl. 2, figs. 13, 14 [non *Aporrhais cornuta* Korobkov, 1949].

1962. *Aporrhais cornutus* Alexeiev, 1945 – Turbina, p. 312, pl. 10, figs. 10, 11 [non *Aporrhais cornuta* Korobkov, 1949].

2019 *Aporrhais* sp. – Popov et al., pl. 3, fig. 5.

Types. Holotype: Museum of the Tyumen Industrial University MTIU K6 (Plate 1: figs 1, 2); paratypes: Museum of the Tyumen Industrial University MTIU K7, MTIU K8, MTIU K45, Slovtsov Museum Complex of Tyumen SMCT MF33788, MF33789.

Etymology. The species is named after Siberia, where Anton Maslennikov collected the holotype.

Diagnosis. A medium-sized, heavily callused *Aporrhais* with long digitations and no digitation adnate to the spire.

Description. High conical shell of medium size [~43 mm], conical spire with about eight whorls, aperture bears two digitations. Protoconch unknown. First three teleoconch whorls rounded, with numerous opisthocyrt growth lines. Fourth teleoconch whorl with opisthocyrt axial ribs, 11 on the abapertural part of the whorl. On the penultimate whorl, ribs strengthened, 6 on abapertural part.

Last whorl with three keels, adapical keel most prominent, with about 5–6 ribs on the abapertural side, apertural side covered with callus, middle keel small with no ribs, abapical keel strongly reduced. Height of last whorl is almost half of the total height. Outer lip formed by two aperturally canaliculated digitations. Lateral adapical digitation is a spearhead-like elongation of adapical keel, long, adapically curved. Middle keel runs into the lateral abapical digitation, short, abapically directed. Abapical keel ends without building a digitation. Inner and outer lip of aperture thickly callused, columella heavily callused, callus covers the last whorl aperturally completely, adapical part of aperture also callused. Rostrum triangular, channeled.

Material. Six specimens: Four shells, MTIU K6, K7, K8, and K45. The shell MTIU K6 is fully preserved, K7 and K8 have a broken apertural extension, and K45 is a fragment. Two shells, MF33788 and MF33789, are stored in the STMC. The specimen with the number MF33788 is fully preserved. These six specimens are figured in plate 1. In the specimen with the number MF33789, the early whorls are broken off.

Measurements. fully preserved specimens: MTIU 6 (holotype), height: 43 mm; SMCT MF33788 (paratype), height: 46 mm.

Locus typicus. Northeastern wall of Kyshtyrla quarry (55°55'15"N, 65°49'26"E), Western Siberia, Trans-Ural region, Russia.

Stratum typicum. Upper part of Tavda Formation, Priabonian, Eocene, Paleogene.

Distribution. Trans-Ural region, including the type locality (Turbina 1959; this paper) and the southern part of Western Siberia near Omsk (Turbina 1962).

Discussion. *Aporrhais siberica* sp. nov. differs from *A. cornuta* by an adspiral digitation, that is absent in *A. siberica* (Plate 2: fig. 1b). The lateral adapical

Plate 1. 1–12. *Aporrhais siberica* sp. nov. (1, 2. Holotype MTIU 6; 3, 4. Paratype SMCT MF33788; 5, 6. Paratype MTIU 7; 7, 8. Paratype MTIU 8; 9, 10. Paratype SMCT MF33789; 11, 12. Paratype MTIU 45.); 13–16. *Aporrhais cornuta* Korobkov, 1949 (13, 14. Korobkov 1949, pl. 65, figs 16a, b respectively, representing a syntype; 15, 16. Alekseev 1963, pl. 16, figs 7, 11 respectively). Scale bar: 10 mm.

digitation is slightly curved in *A. cornuta* (Plate 2: fig. 2a) but more strongly curved in *A. siberica* (Plate 2: fig. 1a). A thick callus covers the apertural part of the last whorl of *Aporrhais siberica* (Plate 2: fig. 1c), while *A. cornuta* only has a thin callus restricted to the columella (Plate 2: fig. 2c) (see also Table 1). Turbina (1959, 1962) considered the Trans-Ural morph as a subadult of *Aporrhais cornuta*. The thick apertural callus, which occurs only in an adult stage, is an argument to reject this assumption.

***Aporrhais cornuta* Korobkov, 1949**

Plate 1: figs 13–16

1949 *Aporrhais cornutus* Alexeev nov. sp. – Korobkov, p. 245, pl. 65, figs. 15, 16a, b. [basionym].

1954 *Apporhais* [sic] *cornutus* Alex. – Ovechkin, p. 76, pl. 9, fig. 22–23.

1955 *Aporrhais cornutus* Alex. – Korobkov, p. 272, pl. 57, figs. 11–13.

1955 *Chenopus* cf. *cornutus* Alex. – Ovechkin, p. 86.

1955 *Chenopus cornutus* Alex. – Ovechkin, p. 87.

- 1955 *Aporrhais* [sic] *cornutus* Alex. – Ovechkin, p. 110.
 1960 *Aporrhais cornutus* Alexeev – Orlov, pl. 21, fig. 10.
 1963 *Chenopus cornutus* n. sp. – Alekseyev, pp. 78–81, pl. 15, figs. 5–16; pl. 16, figs. 5–11.
 1971 *Aporrhais cornuta* Ilyina – Amitrov, pp. 68, 69, pl. 1, fig. 8.
 1972 *Aporrhais* (*Chenopus*) *cornuta* Alex. – Sidorenko, p. 447.
 1975 *Aporrhais cornutus* Alex. – Martynov et al., p. 227, 299, 322.
 1985 *Chenopus cornutus* – Malchevskaya et al., 1985, p. 161.
 1994 *Aporrhais cornutus* Korobkov, 1949 – Amitrov, pp. 104, 105, 107 [partim]
 non 1858 *Rostellaria sowerbyi* Sow. – Abich, 1858, p. 21[557], pl. III [in plate caption: II], fig. 1a, b [= *Aporrhais aralensis* Eichwald, 1868]
 ?non 1859 *Rostellaria Sowerbyi* Sow. – Trautschold, p. 307.
 ?non 1868 *Aporrhais Sowerbyi* Sow. – von Koenen, pp. 158, 159
 non 1953 *Aporrhais cornutus* Alexeev – Il'ina, p. 105, pl. 6, fig. 14, pl. 7, fig. 2a, b [= *Aporrhais* sp.].
 non 1955 *Aporrhais cornutus* (Alexeev) – Il'ina, p. 61, pl. 22, figs. 1, 1a, 4, 5 [= *Aporrhais* sp.].
 non 1958 *Aporrhais* (*Chenopus*) *cornutus* var. – Klyushnikov, pp. 288, 289, pl. 34, fig. 9 [= *Aporrhais* sp.].
 non 1959. *Aporrhais cornutus* – Turbina, pp. 30–31, pl. 2, figs. 13, 14 [= *Aporrhais siberica* n. sp.].
 ?non 1960 *Aporrhais* cf. *speciosa* – Il'ina, p. 285, pl. 3, figs. 12, 13a, 14 [= *A. cornuta* fide Amitrov (1971), not seen]
 non 1962 *Aporrhais cornutus* – Turbina, p. 312, pl. 10, figs. 10, 11 [= *Aporrhais siberica* n. sp.].

Original description by Korobkov, 1949 (in Russian).

Крупная (высота до 57 мм), сильно расширяющаяся книзу, слегка изогнутая раковина, состоящая из 8 оборотов, разделенных глубоким узким швом. Последний оборот большой, несущий на поверхности 3 гранулированных кия, из которых нижний часто бывает совершенно гладкий. Поверхность более ранних оборотов покрыта спиральными ребрышками, количество которых колеблется в пределах от 15 до 18, пересеченными поперечными так, что образуется характерная сетчатая скульптура. На поздних оборотах сетчатая скульптура неотчетливая, вследствие сильного развития спиральных ребер. Устье узкое с 3 характерными пальцевидными отростками наружной губы. Верхний отросток, приросший по всей длине поверхности оборотов, у некоторых экземпляров значительно выступает над спиралью раковины. Второй, изогнутый отросток под углом в 50–70° к первому направлен вбок и

вверх, а нижний прямолинейный отросток примерно под таким же углом к предыдущему — вбок и вниз. Верхний сильно бугорчатый киль поверхности последнего оборота в виде грубого гладкого ребра продолжается на среднем отростке, а средний киль — на нижнем. Пальцевидные отростки с внутренней стороны несут узкие каналы, открывающиеся в устье.

Original description by Korobkov (1949) (translation Trubin, Wieneke). Large (height up to 57 mm), strongly expanding downwards, slightly curved shell, consisting of 8 whorls separated by a deep narrow suture. The last whorl is large, bearing 3 granulated keels on the surface, of which the lower one is often completely smooth. The surface of the earlier whorls is covered by axial ribs, the number of which ranges from 15 to 18, crossed by transverse ones so that a characteristic reticulate sculpture is formed. On later whorls, the reticulate sculpture is indistinct due to the strong development of axial ribs. The aperture is narrow with 3 characteristic finger-like digitations of the outer lip. The adspiral digitation, grown along the entire length of the spire, in some specimens protrudes significantly above the spira. The second, curved process is directed laterally and upwards at an angle of 50–70° to the first one, and the lower rectilinear digitation is directed laterally and downwards at approximately the same angle as the previous one. The upper, strongly tuberculate keel of the surface of the last whorl, in the form of a rough, smooth rib, continues the middle digitation, and the median keel continues the lower digitation. The finger-like digitations on the inner side bear narrow canals that open at the aperture.

Types. Storage location unknown: Syntype 1 represented by Korobkov (1949), pl. 65, fig. 15, syntype 2 represented by Korobkov (1949), pl. 65, fig. 16 a, b.

Locus typicus. „Turnagly“ (=Турнаглы) (in old references also cited as Turangly or Turanghul), northern Aral region, Kazakhstan.

Stratum typicum. Upper Eocene of northern Aral region (Korobkov 1949: 245), Tshegan Formation (Amitrov 1994).

Material. (additionally seen to published specimens): 2 specimens Sedgwick Museum of Earth Sciences, University of Cambridge C11743-4, ex Coll. Bateson (see Lukovitch 1921); 3 specimens Coll. Stichting Schepel Schelp SSS54976; 5 specimens Coll. Elmar Mai, Durbusch; 10 specimens Coll. Ulrich Wieneke, Murnau.

Discussion

The genus *Aporrhais* is treated with a feminine gender (Manganelli et al. 2008), so the correct name is *Aporrhais cornuta*, as Amitrov (1971) pointed out.

Korobkov (1949) and others attributed the name *Aporrhais cornuta* to Alexeev and referred to a manuscript by this author. This manuscript was posthumously published in 1963. Korobkov (1949) and Alekseev (1963) included Abich's (1858) "*Rostellaria sowerbyi* Sow" (Abich 1858, pl. 3, figs 1a. b) in *Aporrhais cornuta*. Korobkov (1949) discovered that the English Eocene species *Rostellaria sowerbyi* (correct name *Aporrhais sowerbii* (Fleming, 1828))

Table 1. Comparison of *Aporrhais siberica* sp. nov. with *A. cornuta*.

Character \ Species	<i>Aporrhais siberica</i> sp. nov.	<i>Aporrhais cornuta</i>
adspiral digitation	no (Plate 2: fig. 1b)	long, protrudes the spire (Plate 2: fig. 2b)
lateral adapical digitation	shorter, stronger curved (Plate 2: fig. 1a)	long, only slightly curved (Plate 2: fig. 2a)
callus	thick, covering the apertural part of the last whorl (Plate 2: fig. 1c)	thin columellar callus (Plate 2: fig. 2c)

Plate 2. Differences between *Aporrhais siberica* (1) and *A. cornuta* (2), a. Lateral adapical digitation, b. Adspirals, c. Callus.

is not conspecific with the specimens from the Crimean Eocene and described the latter as “*Aporrhais cornutus*”, Amitrov (1994) revised the species *Aporrhais cornuta* and attributed it to Korobkov (1949). He also found that the specimen illustrated by Abich (1858, pl. 3, figs 1a, b) should be considered the illustration of the type of *Aporrhais aralensis* Eichwald, 1868, who cited Abich’s figure (Abich 1858, pl. 3, figs 1a, b). It is a much smaller species compared to *Aporrhais cornuta*. He also claimed that only Korobkov’s (1949) specimens should be regarded as syntypes. Although Alekseev (1963) lumped *A. aralensis* and *A. cornuta*, he pointed out how to distinguish them.

Before 1963, Alexeev’s manuscript was cited several times:

- Korobkov (1949) cited Alexeev as the author of *Aporrhais cornuta*, but gave a different description and used different material, as can be concluded from the posthumous publication of the manuscript (Alekseev (1963). Korobkov (1949) should be considered as the describing author (see ICZN 50.1. especially 50.1.1. in combination with article 10.1.1.), as pointed out by Amitrov (1994).
- Il’ina (1953, 1955) used the name “*Aporrhais cornutus*” for a morphologically different, still undescribed species from Kazakhstan. It differs from *Aporrhais cornuta* (Korobkov, 1949) and *A. siberica* sp. nov. by the different ornamentation of the spire and by having a triangular apertural extension missing the long spines (Il’ina 1953).
- Alexeev (1963) also included a drawing from Abich (1858) of *Rostellaria sowerbyi*, p. 21[557], pl.

III [in plate caption: II], fig. 1a, b for his description of *Aporrhais cornutus*. Trautschold (1859) and von Koenen (1868) also cited this drawing.

- Turbina (1959, 1962) used the name *Aporrhais cornutus* for another morphologically different species. This morph is described here as a new species: *Aporrhais siberica*.

Acknowledgments

The authors want to thank Matt Riley, Cambridge, for giving access to the Sedgwick Museum collection, Piet Hessel, Utrecht, Stichting Schepel Schelp, for letting the first author analyze his material, and Elmar Mai, Durbusch, for presenting his material. Sven Nielsen, Valdivia, Thomas Neubauer, München, Alexander Nützel, München, and an unknown reviewer are thanked for their critical reading and commenting. It improved the publication significantly. Working through the literature was made possible by Han Stoutjesdijk, Numansdorp, the Biodiversity Heritage Library, and MolluscaBase.

References

- Abich OWH von (1858) Beiträge zur Paläontologie des asiatischen Russlands. Mémoires de l’Académie des Sciences de Saint-Petersbourg. Sciences mathématiques et physiques 6(7): 537–577[pls. 1–8]. <https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.61029>
- Akhmet’ev MA, Aleksandrova GN, Beniamovskii VN, Vitukhin DI, Glezer ZI, Gnibidenko ZN, Dergachev VD, Dolya ZHA, Zaorizhets

- NI, Kozlova GE, Kul'kova IA, Nikolaeva IA, Ovechkina MN, Radionova EP, Strel'nikova NI (2004) New Data on the Marine Paleogene of the Southwestern Siberian Plate, Paper 2. *Stratigraphy and Geological Correlation* 12(5): 65–86.
- Akhmet'ev MA, Zaporozhets NI, Benyamovskiy VN, Aleksandrova GN, Iakovleva AI, Oreshkina TV (2012) The Paleogene history of the Western Siberian seaway – a connection of the Peri-Tethys to the Arctic Ocean. *Austrian Journal of Earth Sciences* 105(1): 50–67.
- Akhmet'ev MA, Zaporozhets NI, Yakovleva AI, Aleksandrova GN, Beniamovsky VN, Oreshkina TV, Gnibidenko ZN, Dolya ZA (2010) Comparative Analysis of Marine Paleogene Sections and Biota from West Siberia and the Arctic Region. *Stratigraphy and Geological Correlation* 18(6): 635–658. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S0869593810060043>
- Alekseev AK (1963) Paleogene Fauna of Mollusks of the Northern Aral Sea region [Paleogenovaya fauna molljuskov Severnogo Priaralja]. Publishing House of the Academy of Sciences of the Armenian SSR [Erevan, Izdatel'stvo Akademii Nauk Armjanskoj SSR], Yerevan, 230 pp. [in Russian]
- Amitov OV (1971) Oligocene complexes of gastropods of Mangyshlak and southwestern Ustyurt [Oligotsenovyye komplekсы gastropod mangyshlaka i yugo-zapadnogo Ustyurta]. In: Zhizhchenko BP, Ivanova VA (Eds) *Cenozoic Stratigraphy and Paleogeography of the Oil and Gas Areas of the South of the Soviet Union* [Stratigrafiya i paleogeografiya kaynozoya gazoneftenosnykh oblastey yuga Sovetskogo Soyuz], vol. 31/39–32/40, 65–81. Nedra, Moscow [Moskva: Nedra].
- Amitov OV (1994) Gastropods of the Chegan formation (Transcaspiian, Eocene); 1. Previous knowledge and problems of nomenclature [Gastropody cheganskoy svity (eocen Zakaspiya). St. 1. Izuchennost' i voprosy nomenklatury]. *Bulletin of Moscow Society of Naturalists, geological series* [Vestnik Moskovskogo obshchestva yestestvoispytateley, Otdel geologii] 69(5): 69–110. [in Russian]
- Amitov OV (2005) Complexes of marine gastropods of the Eocene and Oligocene of western Kazakhstan [Komplekсы morskikh gastropod eotsena i oligotsena Zapadnogo Kazakhstana]. *Bulletin of Moscow Society of Naturalists, geological series* [Vestnik Moskovskogo obshchestva yestestvoispytateley, Otdel geologii] 80(1): 37–55. [in Russian]
- Eichwald E (1865–1868) *Lethaea Rossica ou Paléontologie de la Russie. Moyenne Periode. E. Schweizerbart, Stuttgart, [XXXV +] 1304 pp.* <https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.52391>
- Fleming J (1828) *A history of British animals, exhibiting the descriptive characters and systematical arrangement of genera and species of quadrupeds, birds, reptiles, fishes, mollusca, and Radiata of the United Kingdom.* Edinburgh, [XXIII +] 565 pp. <https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.12859>
- Gnibidenko ZN, Kuzmina OB, Levicheva AV (2020) Regional Magnetostratigraphy of the Upper Cretaceous and the Cretaceous–Paleogene Boundary in Southern West Siberia as Applied to Complitation of the Cretaceous Magnetic-Polarity Scale. *Russian Geology and Geophysics* 61(9): 1028–1035. <https://doi.org/10.15372/RGG2019170>
- Gray JE (1850) [text]. In: Gray ME, *Figures of molluscous animals, selected from various authors.* Longman, Brown, Green and Longmans, London, 4, [IV +] 219 pp.
- Iakovleva AI, Heilmann-Clausen C (2010) Eocene dinoflagellate cyst biostratigraphy of research borehole 011-BP, Omsk Region, southwestern Siberia. *Palynology* 34(2): 195–232. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01916121003629974>
- Iakovleva AI (2000) Biostratigraphical and paleogeographical significance of the Paleocene–Eocene dinoflagellates in Western Siberia and adjacent regions (Petchora depression and Turgay trough). *GFF* 122: 82–83. <https://doi.org/10.1080/11035890001221082>
- Iakovleva AI (2011) Palynological reconstruction of the Eocene marine palaeoenvironments in south of Western Siberia. *Acta Palaeobotanica* 51(2): 229–248.
- Il'ina AP (1953) Mollusks of the Chegan Formation from the northern chinks of Ustyurt [Mollyuski cheganskoy svity severnykh chinkov Ustyurta]. In: *Paleontological Serie* [Paleontologicheskii sbornik], 93–134. State Scientific and Technical Publishing House of Oil and Mining Fuel Literature [Gosudarstvennoye nauchno-tekhnicheskoye izdatel'stvo neftyanoy i gorno-toplivnoy literatury], Leningrad and Moscow. [in Russian]
- Il'ina AP (1955) Paleogene Mollusks of Northern Ustyurt [Mollyuski paleogena Severnogo Ustyurta]. State Scientific and Technical Publishing House of Oil and Mining Fuel Literature [Gosudarstvennoye nauchno-tekhnicheskoye izdatel'stvo neftyanoy i gorno-toplivnoy literatury], Leningrad, 163 pp. [in Russian]
- Il'ina AP (1960) Lower Oligocene mollusks Mangyshlak, [Nizhneoligotsenovyye mollyuski Mangyshlaka]. *Proceedings of VNIGRI, New Series* [Tr. VNIGRI, Novaya seriya,], 154(2): 265–298. [in Russian]
- Klyushkov MN (1958) *Stratigraphy and Fauna of the Lower Tertiary Sediments of Ukraine; [Stratigrafiya i fauna nizhnetretichnykh otlozheniy Ukrainy].* Publishing House of the Academy of Sciences of the Ukrainian SSR [Izdatel'stvo akademii nauk Ukrainskoy SSR], Kyiv, 549 pp. [in Russian]
- Koenen A (1868) Über die Unter-Oligocaene Tertiaer-Fauna vom Aralsee. *Bulletin Société Impériale des naturalistes de Moscou* 41(1–2): 144–172.
- Korobkov IA (1949) Gastropoda. In: Ryabinin AN, Korobkov IA (Eds) (1949) *Atlas of Guiding Forms of Fossil Faunas of the USSR. Paleogene*, 231–269, pls. 63–71.
- Korobkov IA (1955) Reference book and methodological guide to tertiary mollusks. *Gastropods* [Spravochnik i metodicheskoe rukovodstvo po tretichnym molliuskam. Bruhonogie]. State Scientific and Technical Oil Research [Gosudarstvennii Nauchno-Tekhnicheskii Issledovanie Nefti], Leningrad, 795 pp. [in Russian]
- Kuzmina OB, Lebedeva NK, Shchuclin NE (2021) Palynostratigraphy of the Cretaceous and Paleogene Sediments of Chelyabinsk Oblast, South Transurals. *Stratigraphy and Geological Correlation* 29(2): 215–240. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S0869593821020040>
- Lukovitch MT (1921) A new contribution to the knowledge of the Lower Tertiary Mollusca of the Aral Sea. *Société des Sciences Naturelle Croate* 33: 157–174.
- Malchevskaya TM, Kulikov MV, Vitlin AV (1985) *Catalogue of Holotypes of Fauna and Flora Species stored in GNIGR Museum Issue 2, Part II - Meso-Cenozoic; [Katalog golotipov vidov fauny i flory, khraryashchikhsya v Muzeye GNIGR Vypusk 2, Chast' II - Mezokaynozoy].* Ministry of Geology of the USSR [Ministerstvo geologii SSSR], Leningrad, 254 pp. [in Russian]
- Malyshkina TP (2021) *Striatolamia tchelkarnurensis* Glickman (Elasmobranchii: Lamniformes), the Youngest Valid *Striatolamia* Species. *Paleontological Journal* 2(2): 77–87. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S0031030121020088>
- Malyshkina TP (2006) Late Eocene scyliorhinid sharks from the Trans-Urals, Russia. *Acta Palaeontologica Polonica* 51(3): 465–475.

- Malyshkina TP (2012) New sharks of the genus *Abdouina* (Carcharhiniformes: Carcharhinidae) from the Upper Eocene of the Trans-Ural Region. *Paleontological Journal* 46(4): 60–67. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S0031030112040053>
- Manganelli G, Spadini V, Fiorentino V (2008) The lost *Aporrhais* species from the Italian Pliocene: *A. peralata* (Sacco, 1893) (Gastropoda, Caenogastropoda). *Journal of Conchology* 39: 493–515.
- Mantell G (1822) *The Fossils of the South Downs; or Illustrations of the Geology of Sussex*. Lupton Relfe, London, 1–328, pls. I–XLII. <https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.44924>
- Marrama G, Carnevale G, Smirnov PV, Trubin YS, Krivet J (2019) First report of Eocene Gadiform fishes from the Trans-Urals (Sverdlovsk and Tyumen regions, Russia). *Journal of Paleontology* 93(5): 1001–1009. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jpa.2019.15>
- Martynov VA, Sigov AP, Chirva SA (1975) West Siberian Plate [Zapadno-Sibirskaya plita]. In: Nalivkin DV (Ed.) *Paleogene of USSR [Paleogenovaya sistema SSSR]*, 315–328. Bosom [Nedra], Moscow. [in Russian]
- Mendes da Costa E (1778–1779) *Historia naturalis testaceorum britanniae or the British Conchology; containing the descriptions and other particulars of natural history of the shells of Great Britain and Ireland: illustrated with figures*. Printed for the author, and sold by Millan, B. White, Elmsley, and Robson, London, XII, 254, VII pp., 17 pls. <https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.13179>
- Nesterov II, Smirnov PV, Konstantinov AO, Gursky H-J (2021) Types, features, and resource potential of Palaeocene–Eocene siliceous rock deposits of the West Siberian Province. *International Geology Review* 63(14): 504–525. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00206814.2020.1719370>
- Orlov YA (1960) *Principles of Paleontology, Mollusca - Gastropoda [Printsipy paleologii, Mollyuski - Bryukhoniye]*. State Publishing House of Geological Literature [Gosudarstvennoye izdatel'stvo geologicheskoy literatury], Moscow, 360 pp. [in Russian]
- Ovechkin NK (1954) Middle Paleogene deposits of the Turgai Depression and the Northern Aral Sea region [Otlozheniya srednego paleogena Turgayskoy vpadiny i Severnogo Priaral'ya]. State Publishing House of Geological Literature [Gosudarstvennoye izdatel'stvo geologicheskoy literatury], Moscow, 170 pp. [in Russian]
- Ovechkin NK (1955) *Geology of the southwestern part of the Turgai Depression [Geologiya yugo-zapadnoy chasti Turgayskogo progiba]*. State Publishing House of Geological Literature [Gosudarstvennoye izdatel'stvo geologicheskoy literatury], Moscow, 156 pp. [in Russian]
- Palcu DV, Krugsmann W (2022) The dire straits of Paratethys: gateways to the anoxic giant of Eurasia. *Geological Society, London, Special Publications*: 523. <https://doi.org/10.1144/SP523-2021-73>
- Podobina VM (1975) Foraminifers from the Upper Cretaceous and Paleogene of the West Siberian Lowland and their significant for stratigraphy [Foraminifery verkhnego mela i paleogena Zapadno-Sibirskoy nizmennosti i ikh znacheniye dlya stratigrafii]. Tomsk University Publishing House [Izdatel'stvo Tomskogo universiteta], Tomsk, 163 pp. [in Russian]
- Podobina VM (1998) Paleogene foraminifera and biostratigraphy of Western Siberia [Foraminifery i biostratografiya paleogena Zapadnoy Sibiri]. Tomsk University Publishing House [Izdatel'stvo Tomskogo universiteta], Tomsk, 334 pp. [in Russian]
- Podobina VM (2020) Paleogene foraminifera and biostratigraphy of Western Siberia [Biostratografiya i foraminifer paleogena Zapadnoy Sibiri]. Tomsk University Publishing House [Izdatel'stvo Tomskogo universiteta], Tomsk, 276 pp. [in Russian]
- Popov SV, Trubin YS, Smirnov PV, Ordowskyi VV, Goncharova IA, Amritov OV (2019) On the Taxonomic Composition of Mollusks from the Tavda Formation of Western Siberia. *Paleontological Journal* 53(1): 20–29. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S0031030119010076>
- Ryabinin AN, Korobkov IA [Ed.] (1949) *Atlas of Guiding Forms of Fossil Faunas of the USSR. Paleogene [Atlas napravlyayushchikh form iskopayemykh faun SSSR. Paleogen]*. State Publishing House of Geological Literature [Gosudarstvennoye izdatel'stvo geologicheskoy literatury], Moscow, 367 pp. [in Russian]
- Schwarzhan WW, Smirnov PV, Trubin YS, Ordowskyi V (2021) First record of otoliths from the Eocene of Western Siberia. *Cybium* 45(1): 79–80. <https://doi.org/10.26028/cybium/2021-451-009>
- Sidorenko AV (1972) *Geology of USSR, Central Kazakhstan [Geologiya SSSR, Tsentral'nyy Kazakhstan]*. Bosom [Nedra], Moscow, 532 pp. [in Russian]
- Smirnov PV, Deryagina OI, Novoselov AA, Trubin YS, Batalin GA, Gareev BI, Plyusnin AV (2019) Eocene Tavda Formation clays: lithochemical and sedimentological aspects (Kyshtylinskoe deposit, West Siberia). *Bulletin of the Tomsk Polytechnic University. Geo Assets Engineering* 330(11): 130–144. <https://doi.org/10.18799/24131830/2019/11/2357>
- Subbotina NN, Alekseychik-Mitskevich LS, Baranovskaya OF, Bulatova ZI, Bulynnikova SP, Dubrovskaya NF, Kisel'man EN, Kozlova GE, Kuzina VI, Kiseleva OT, Krivoborskiy VV, Ushakova MV, Freyman YV (1964) Foraminifera from the Cretaceous and Paleogene deposits of Western Siberia [Foraminifery melovykh i paleogenovykh otlozheniy Zapadno-Sibirskoy nizmennosti]. Bosom [Nedra], Leningrad, 456 pp. [in Russian]
- Trautschold H (1859) Ueber Petrefakten vom Aralsee. *Bulletin Société Impériale des naturalistes de Moscou* 32(1–2): 303–322.
- Trubin YS (2018) Family Naticidae of the Tavda Formation (Eocene, Western Siberia). *Ruthenica, Russian Malacological Journal* 28(1): 11–17. [https://doi.org/10.35885/10.35885/ruthenica.2018.28\(1\).2](https://doi.org/10.35885/10.35885/ruthenica.2018.28(1).2)
- Trubin YS, Marinov VA, Smirnov PV, Novoselov AA, Langer MR (2024) Upper Eocene benthic foraminiferal assemblages from the Western Siberia (Trans-Ural Region): a multi-proxy approach to infer environmental changes. *Micropaleontology* 70 (3): 287–299. <https://doi.org/10.47894/mpal.70.3.07>
- Turbina AS (1959) Some species of bivalves and gastropods of the Paleogene of the West Siberian lowland [Nekotoryye vidy dvustvorok i bryukhoniye paleogena Zapadno-Sibirskoy nizmennosti]. In *Materials on paleontology and stratigraphy of Western Siberia [Materialy po paleologii i stratigrafii Zapadnoy Sibiri]*. Leningrad: State Publishing House of Geological Literature [Gosudarstvennoye izdatel'stvo geologicheskoy literatury], 19–36. [in Russian]
- Turbina AS (1962) Gastropod mollusks of Tertiary marine sediments [Bryukhoniye mollyuski tretichnykh morskikh otlozheniy]. In *Biostratigraphy of Mesozoic and Tertiary deposits of Western Siberia [Biostratografiya mezozoyskikh i tretichnykh otlozheniy Zapadnoy Sibiri]*. State Publishing House of Geological Literature [Gosudarstvennoye izdatel'stvo geologicheskoy literatury], Leningrad, 311–312. [in Russian]